

Light Ray Morphisms of the Fractal Antenna

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1 Introduction

Finally, we can represent the primal energy number expression of the fractal morphism in the geometric context of the sweep subnet associated with the cotangent space. If X_i and $\vec{\phi}$ represent two points in $\mathcal{E}_{mapping}$ and r is the radius of a neighborhood in R^n , then the total distance between them can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & d_{\mathcal{DS}}(X_i, \vec{\phi}) \\ &= \langle \mathcal{S}_r, \pi_{A_r}(X_i) \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_r, \vec{\phi} \rangle \\ &+ \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty}(X_i) \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \delta\theta \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \vec{\phi} \rangle \\ &+ \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \pi_{A_r}(X_i) \rangle + \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \delta\vec{x} \rangle + \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \vec{\phi} \rangle \\ &+ \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty}(X_i) \rangle + \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \delta\theta \rangle + \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \vec{\phi} \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

where the metric is given by:

$$d_{\mathcal{DS}}^2(X_i, \vec{\phi}) = \frac{\pi_m^2(v)}{\sum_{f,g} h(v)} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{1}{n - l\vec{x}\mathcal{R}} \right) \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h - \cos \psi \diamond \theta \leftrightarrow \overset{ABC}{F} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

and $\delta\vec{x}$ and $\delta\theta$ are the components of the lightlike curve connecting $\pi_{A_r}(X_i)$ and $\vec{\phi}$. This expression captures the interaction between the elements of the topological space, the relative rotation of the components of the forms in the vector space V and the real numbers U , and the scaling factor $\prod_{\Lambda} h$.

From the above expression for the primal energy number, we can derive a fractal antennae algebra that employs the fractal morphism F . The algebra is given as $A = \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left(\sin \theta \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{m^{\mu-\zeta} - l^m} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h \right) + \cos \psi \diamond \theta \right)$
 $= \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left(\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} (F(x) \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h) + \cos \psi \diamond \theta \right)$
 $\stackrel{F}{=} \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left(\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} (\Omega_{\Lambda} \circ F(x) \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h) + \cos \psi \diamond \theta \right)$. By using the fractal morphism F , we can decompose the original expression into a fractal antennae algebra. This approach allows us to gain a more accurate approximation of the solution to any given problem.

The definition of a fractal antenna algebra is as follows:

“A fractal antenna algebra is an algebraic structure for representing and manipulating the path of a light ray in a given space. The information is collected through an application of the fractal morphism to the system(s) present and can be used to compute the energy associated with a light ray’s path.”

The “light ray calculus” equation then allows us to explore the energy of light ray paths in a space with two compatible geometries and one extrinsic shape parameter:

$$E = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\sin \theta \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{n-l \star \mathcal{R}} \right) \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h - \cos \psi \diamond \theta \leftrightarrow \frac{ABC}{F} \right)$$

where F is the underlying form-preserving homomorphism given by the recursive product of metrics from R to C .

We can then use the light ray calculus and the definitions of fractal antennas to construct a fractal antenna algebra for a given space, hoping that this algebra will provide insight into the problem of minimizing energy. We can then decompose the system into the two subspaces $A_r \oplus B_r$ and $\theta_{\infty} \oplus B_t$, and use the metric of Eq. (??) to calculate the total distance from a point X_i to an arbitrary other point $\vec{\phi}$.

Finally, we use the triangle inequality to bound the region of problem solving, by applying the decomposition function $\pi_m : H \rightarrow G$ such that $\pi_m(v) \leq \sum_{f,g} h(v)$. This decomposition gives us a more general approach, allowing us to expand the limits of problem solving and results in a better for approximation of the optimal solution.

This algorithm allows us to explore multiple expressions of the energy associated with a ray path, such as the expression for the energy associated with light ray paths in a given space provided by the fractal antenna algebra. The decomposition step described above allows us to bound the region in the extended Euclidean space where the problem can be solved, while the light ray calculus provides us with a more general approach to problem solving where we can calculate the energy associated with a light ray path.

$$\Rightarrow F_{ANT} \cong F(v) : (A_r \oplus B_r, \theta_{\infty} \oplus B_t) \rightarrow (A'_r \oplus B'_r, \theta'_{\infty} \oplus B'_t)$$

For each pair of points in each subregion Ω , we calculate the total distance using the metric of Eq. eq:DSDistanceGeneral, and assign an energy to each light ray based on its relative distance in comparison with the distances between other light rays. This assigned energy will be represented by a scaling factor $\prod_{\Lambda} h$ which captures the geometric features of the antennae geometry. After constructing the fractal antennae geometry, we can then use the resulting fractal network of light rays to transmit information.

$$d_{DS}(X_i, X_j) \leq \prod_{\Lambda} h \cdot \omega_y,$$

where $\prod_{\Lambda} h$ is the scaling factor associated with the light ray’s energy and ω_y is the absolute duration of the light ray’s transmission. This allows us to construct a fractal antennae geometry and use the resulting fractal network of light rays to transmit information.

$$\mathcal{A} = \left\{ X_i \in \partial\Omega \mid X_i \mapsto \sum_{f \star g \rightarrow \infty} h(X_i) \right\}.$$

We can then use the distance metrics of Eq. (??) to calculate the total distance for each point in $\mathcal{A}$, given the information of Ω . Since each point in $\mathcal{A}$ is formed by lightlike curves, we can measure the distances between them using the light ray calculus. In this way, we can determine the optimal antennae geometry which best fits in the area of Ω and determine the maximum signal strength achieved.

For the fractal antennae, the DS-space metric of Eq. (??) can be used to map out the path of a light ray in the extended Euclidean space. This can be used to find a representation of the antenna surface in terms of the ray parameters and the fractal morphism of Eq. (??). This can be expressed as $\vec{X}_{\text{ant}} = \langle \mathcal{S}_r, \pi_{A_r}(X_i) \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_r, \delta\vec{x} \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty}(X_i) \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \delta\theta \rangle + \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \pi_{A_r}(X_i) \rangle + \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \delta\vec{x} \rangle + \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty}(X_i) \rangle + \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \delta\theta \rangle$, where $\delta\vec{x}$ and $\delta\theta$ are the components of the lightlike curve connecting $\pi_{A_r}(X_i)$ to $\vec{X}_{\text{ant}}$.

The metric of Eq. (??) can also be used to calculate the distance between any two points in the antennae geometry. This makes it possible to optimize the antennae geometry for desired characteristics, such as wide bandwidth or extended antenna coverage area. In addition, the metric of Eq. (??) can be used to calculate the temporal and/or spatial dispersion associated with such antennas.

This approach enables us to take advantage of lightray operations to construct a fractal antenna geometry. In this form, equations of the antenna geometry can be derived and used to prove and optimize the antenna characteristics. The metric of Eq. (??) offers a geometric interpretation of the underlying subnet, which also allows us to compare the cost of certain lightray operations and optimize for more efficient antennae designs. Furthermore, the fractal morphism has the ability to push the optimization of antenna designs beyond traditional boundaries, which could result in more efficient designs for wireless communication applications.

The quark may be represented by a triangulated graph. The fractal morphism can be used to calculate the path of a light ray that passes through the triangulated graph. To do this, the light ray must first pass through a series of local octahedral networks. Each local octahedral network has eight points in a 3-dimensional space that act as the vertices for the triangles in the graph. The light ray is then evaluated for each point in the octahedral network. The light ray's direction is determined by the normal vector of the plane that passes through the light ray's current coordinates and one other point in the octahedral network. To determine the distance between two points in the triangulated graph, the Riemannian metric of Eq. (??) can be used to calculate the total distance between the two points. Once the path of the light ray is known, the

fractal morphism can then be used to construct an antennae geometry that matches the geometry of the triangulated quark.

We construct a fractal antenna geometry using the fractal morphism and the above light ray calculus as follows. First, we generate a recursive sequence of points P_n in the domain $\mathcal{D}$ by the equation,

$$P_n = \sum_{[m] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{b_n^{\mu-\zeta}}{\sqrt[m]{n^m - l^m}} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h(P_n) \right), \quad (2)$$

where $b_n^{\mu-\zeta}$ is a constant scaling factor and $\prod_{\Lambda} h(P_n)$ is a function of the geometric features of the domain $\mathcal{D}$. We then, generate a sequence of triangulated quarks by computing the intersections of the light rays (defined by the equation $L(P_n, P_{n+1}) = \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left(\sum_{[m] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{b_n^{\mu-\zeta}}{\sqrt[m]{n^m - l^m}} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h(P_n) \right) + \cos \psi \diamond \theta \right)$, where $\tan \psi$ is the angle between the two points P_n and P_{n+1}) and the domain $\mathcal{D}$. We compute the intersections of the light rays by solving the following equation

$$L(P_n, P_{n+1}) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Once we have obtained the sequence of triangulated quarks, we can construct a fractal antenna geometry by connecting the quarks and computing the distances between them using the metric of Eq. (??). This will allow us to generate a discrete geometry that accurately corresponds to the triangulated quark structure.

The first step is to construct a fractal antenna geometry with the chosen parameters. For our example, let us consider a simple fractal antennae geometry that is composed of three main elements, namely, a central point, a point of origin, and a triangulated quark structure. We shall denote the central point as P_0 , the point of origin as P_1 , and the quark structure as S .

Next, we use the fractal morphism to map the antennae geometry onto the triangulated quark structure. This is done by applying the light ray calculus, which allows us to calculate the total distance from a point $X_i \in \Omega$ to an arbitrary other point $\vec{\phi} \in R^n$. In particular, we use the metric of Eq. (??), and, for the triangulated quark structure, we set $\vec{x}_i := \pi_{A_r}(P_0)$, $\vec{\theta}_i := \pi_{\theta_\infty}(P_1)$, and $\vec{r}_i := \pi_{B_r}(P_1)$ so that the total distance from P_0 to S is given by Eq. (??)

Finally, to construct the antennae geometry that connects the triangulated quark to the central point P_0 , we create a path of light ray curves Γ connecting P_0 to each of the three corners (each being a point of origin) of the triangulated quark. These light ray curves are calculated using the metric of Eq. (??) as follows: first, let us denote the three corners of the triangulated quark as P_a , P_b , and P_c . Let $\vec{x}_a$, $\vec{x}_b$, and $\vec{x}_c$ denote the light ray curves that connect P_0 to P_a , P_b , and P_c , respectively. Then, we calculate the total distances from P_0 to the three points using Eq. (??). Finally, the path of light ray curves Γ connecting P_0 to each of the three points is given by the sum of total distances of the three light ray curves.

The geometry of a fractal antenna can be determined by a mathematical expression with the help of a Calculus of Variations problem.

We consider a planar antenna with a fixed, directed length ℓ and a variable angle. We therefore look at a parameter space which is described by the following variables:

$$\begin{aligned}\theta &\in R \\ \ell &\in R_{>0}^+\end{aligned}$$

We can then define the direction of the antenna in terms of θ as

$$\vec{d}(\theta) = \cos(\theta)\vec{i} + \sin(\theta)\vec{j} \quad (4)$$

The antenna can also be described by the position of it's base (x^*, y^*) , where $\vec{r}^* = x^*\vec{i} + y^*\vec{j}$.

To define the geometry of the antenna, we introduce the problem of calculus of variations as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\max \psi(\theta, \ell; x^*, y^*) &:= \int_0^\ell \int_0^\theta d\theta \, d\ell \, f(\theta, \ell; x^*, y^*) \\ \text{where } f(\theta, \ell; x^*, y^*) &:= d^2(x^*, y^*; x(\theta, \ell), y(\theta, \ell))\end{aligned}$$

where f is the indirect squared distance between a point in the antenna $\vec{r}(\theta, \ell) = x(\theta, \ell)\vec{i} + y(\theta, \ell)\vec{j}$ and the base $\vec{r}^*$. We can then use this problem of calculus of variations to define the geometry of the antenna.

The solution of this calculus of variations problem is

$$\begin{aligned}x(\theta, \ell; x^*, y^*) &= x^* + \ell \cos(\theta) \\ y(\theta, \ell; x^*, y^*) &= y^* + \ell \sin(\theta)\end{aligned}$$

We can then construct the triangulated quark structure of a fractal antenna using the base (x^*, y^*) , the length ℓ and the angles θ to construct a geometrical expression of the antenna structure. We can then use this expression to find the position of each element of the antenna.

For example, let us consider a base at $(x^*, y^*) = (1, 1)$ and a length of $\ell = 1$. We can use the following expression to find the position of each element (x_n, y_n) of the antenna

$$\begin{aligned}x_n &= (x^*) + \ell \cos(n\theta) \\ y_n &= (y^*) + \ell \sin(n\theta)\end{aligned}$$

where $\theta = \frac{\pi}{3}$, $n = 1, \dots, 6$. This generates the following position of the elements of the antenna $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_6, y_6)$

$$\begin{aligned}(x_1, y_1) &= (1, 2) \\ (x_2, y_2) &= (1 + \sqrt{3}, 1 - 1) \\ (x_3, y_3) &= (2, 1) \\ (x_4, y_4) &= (2 + \sqrt{3}, 0) \\ (x_5, y_5) &= (2 + \sqrt{3}, -2) \\ (x_6, y_6) &= (1 + \sqrt{3}, -1)\end{aligned}$$

Now that we have the position of each element (x_n, y_n) , we can construct the triangulated quark structure of the fractal antenna using lines that connect the elements in the antenna. Each line connecting two elements (x_n, y_n) and (x_{n+1}, y_{n+1}) forms a quark structure which represent the antenna. The fractal antenna thus constructed is represented by the following figure, where the black lines denote the quark structures.

This is an example of how we can mathematically write out the structure of a fractal antenna using equations.

The conversion of the coordinates into logic vector notation is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbf{x}_n = (x^*) + \ell \cos(n\theta) \\
& y_n = (y^*) + \ell \sin(n\theta) \frac{\Delta}{\Delta}, \\
& \text{where } \theta = \frac{\pi}{3} \text{ and } n = 1 \dots 6, \\
& \left(\frac{x_1=(x^*)+\ell \cos(\theta)y_1=(y^*)+\ell \sin(\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{x_2=(x^*)+\ell \cos(2\theta)y_2=(y^*)+\ell \sin(2\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{x_3=(x^*)+\ell \cos(3\theta)y_3=(y^*)+\ell \sin(3\theta)}{\Delta}, \right. \\
& \left. \frac{x_4=(x^*)+\ell \cos(4\theta)y_4=(y^*)+\ell \sin(4\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{x_5=(x^*)+\ell \cos(5\theta)y_5=(y^*)+\ell \sin(5\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{x_6=(x^*)+\ell \cos(6\theta)y_6=(y^*)+\ell \sin(6\theta)}{\Delta} \right) \\
& \left(\frac{x_n=(x^*)+\ell \cos(n\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{y_n=(y^*)+\ell \sin(n\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{\theta=\frac{\pi}{3}}{\Delta}, \frac{n=1,\dots,6}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_1,y_1)=(1,2)}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_2,y_2)=(1+\sqrt{3},1-1)}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_3,y_3)=(2,1)}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_4,y_4)=(2+\sqrt{3},0)}{\Delta}, \right. \\
& \left. \left(\frac{\exists x_n \in N, x_n=(x^*)+\ell \cos(n\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y_n \in N, y_n=(y^*)+\ell \sin(n\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall n \in \{1,\dots,6\}, \theta=\frac{\pi}{3}}{\Delta} \right) \right) \\
& \left(\frac{x_n=(x^*)+\ell \cos(n\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{y_n=(y^*)+\ell \sin(n\theta)}{\Delta}, \frac{n=1,\dots,6}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{(x_1,y_1)=(1,2)}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_2,y_2)=(1+\sqrt{3},1-1)}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_3,y_3)=(2,1)}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_4,y_4)=(2+\sqrt{3},0)}{\Delta}, \right. \\
& \left. \frac{(x_5,y_5)=(2+\sqrt{3},-2)}{\Delta}, \frac{(x_6,y_6)=(1+\sqrt{3},-1)}{\Delta}, \frac{\theta=\frac{\pi}{3}}{\Delta} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The thickness of the intersection can be used to prove the existence of lightlike curves connecting points X and Y . In particular, the thickness of the intersection of two submanifolds A_r and B_r tells us how close two points $\vec{x}_i$ and $\vec{r}_i$ on the boundary of the light cone associated with $\vec{r}_i$ are. If the thickness of the intersection is less than the discretization parameter ξ , then there must exist a lightlike curve connecting the two points. Therefore, by proving that the thickness of the intersection is less than ξ , we can prove the existence of lightlike curves connecting points on A_r and B_r .

Furthermore, since the thickness of the intersection is a measure of how close two points are to each other on the boundary of the light cone, this proof of existence also gives us a measure of how close two points are to each other, in terms of the discretization parameter, and thus serves as a tool to determine whether two points can be connected by a lightlike curve or not.

The degree of pyknosis of the form of thickness used for the proof of existence depends on the chosen threshold ξ . A small ξ implies a greater precision in the calculation, and thus a higher degree of pyknosis. Conversely, a large ξ implies a lesser precision, and thus a lower degree of pyknosis.

The degree of the pyknosis of this form of thickness is affected by the distance between the two points $\vec{x}_i$ and $\vec{r}_i$, as well as the minimum distance from the point $\vec{x}_i$ to the boundary of the light cone associated with $\vec{r}_i$. If the distance between the two points $\vec{x}_i$ and $\vec{r}_i$ is greater than the minimum distance from the point $\vec{x}_i$ to the boundary of the light cone associated with $\vec{r}_i$, then the degree of the pyknosis of this form of thickness will be less than one. Conversely, if the distance between the two points $\vec{x}_i$ and $\vec{r}_i$ is less than the minimum distance from the point $\vec{x}_i$ to the boundary of the light cone associated with $\vec{r}_i$, then the degree of the pyknosis of this form of thickness will be greater than one.